
A QUADRANT MODEL FOR A LEAN PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE OF DOSING SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces a novel, lean approach to predictive maintenance for dosing systems, validated within the use case of exhaust gas after-treatment for diesel engines. Unlike traditional methods, which require additional sensor technologies and complex model architectures, the proposed lean quadrant model uses only hydraulic parameters. The differential pressure, volume flow, and pump rotational speed serve as the basis for the monitoring approach, as they represent fundamental control variables within the dosing system. By capturing the behavior of assets within a hydraulic resistance, the system detects anomalies such as clogging, pump wear, or leaks with high sensitivity. Experimental validation demonstrates a model accuracy within a standard deviation of 2.31 ml/min for volume flow monitoring, at a nominal flow of 3000 ml/min, and a standard deviation of 0.04 bar for differential pressure, at a nominal value of 4 bar, demonstrating its high sensitivity. The model's computational efficiency enables a lean implementation, providing a cost-effective solution that allows for a differentiation between monitoring the pump's health and the asset's status within the quadrant modeling approach.

Keywords predictive maintenance · lean maintenance · small data · prognostics and health management · dosing systems · condition monitoring · condition-based maintenance · engineering asset management

1 Introduction

Industry 4.0 involves the enhanced connectivity and digitization of production processes through the use of intelligent sensors and interconnected systems. By utilizing intelligent sensors and actuators, automated data analysis, and interconnected systems, processes are becoming more efficient, adjustable, and resource-conserving. Digital transformation enables the use of intelligent modeling approaches, which significantly increase the productivity and reliability of industrial processes (Ghobakhloo 2020). In increasingly complex industrial environments, where machines and processes are interconnected, the interaction between subsystems is vital for their overall performance. Digital transformation enhances these environments through intelligent sensors and networked controls, making subsystem interaction strategic. Especially within the context of fluid management, where the precise and reliable delivery of liquid substances is essential, the interaction between complex machinery and dosing units as subsystems becomes a decisive factor in achieving consistent performance, product quality, and operational reliability. As such subsystems, dosing units operate at the interface between process control, fluid handling, and complex machinery. Their applications include chemical and pharmaceutical manufacturing, water treatment, heat control, as well as the oil and gas sector, and the transport industry (Nesbitt 2006). Dosing systems are crucial in all sectors where complex machines, production processes, or technical products require precise and reliable fluid media. The function of dosing systems is to accurately control the delivery of liquids, which often has significant implications for product quality, safety, and process efficiency in the respective industrial applications. Their reliability is critical – malfunctions can lead to production losses, safety hazards, or environmental and regulatory violations. Hence, dosing systems must operate under challenging conditions, including exposure to corrosive substances, fluctuating flow demands, and strict hygienic or safety requirements. Therefore, dosing pumps represent not only the heart of these subsystem assets but also vital elements in ensuring quality, compliance, and efficiency across various industrial applications. This increasing demand for integration is not limited to stationary industrial processes – it also extends to mobile and hybrid systems operating under stringent regulatory and environmental constraints (Volk 2013).

Fluid-handling systems in the transport and energy sectors are crucial for controlling emissions and improving engine efficiency, which requires intelligent monitoring and maintenance strategies (Regulation (EU) 2024/1610 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 May 2024 amending Regulation (EU) 2019/1242 as regards strengthening the CO₂ emission performance standards for new heavy-duty vehicles and integrating reporting obligations, amending Regulation (EU) 2018/858 and repealing Regulation (EU) 2018/956). However, unexpected failures can still disrupt operational processes, leading to unexpected downtime, which manufacturers and users must bear. Predictive maintenance has, therefore, become an established approach in the field and within the literature to tackle this issue more effectively (Zonta et al. 2020). Predictive maintenance adopts a flexible approach, incorporating real-time monitoring and data analysis to replace rigid service intervals with condition-based actions. Intelligent algorithms enable users to detect early signs of failures, reducing the risk of potential problems and avoiding scenarios that could lead to significant breakdowns. Sensor-driven methods allow users to customize maintenance schedules, minimize the risk of unexpected failures, and prolong the lifespan of critical components within systems. While the setup costs for predictive maintenance are upfront and involve integration work, its benefits, including reduced total maintenance costs and improved equipment uptime, make it an essential step toward reliable and cost-efficient dosing systems. However, conventional predictive maintenance approaches for dosing units often rely on additional sensors or indirect indicators, which increase system complexity (Nunes et al. 2023). Moreover, existing methods may not fully capture the dynamic hydraulic behavior of these subsystems under varying operating conditions. To address this, the present work investigates a condition monitoring strategy that relies solely on hydraulic system parameters, thereby offering a cost-efficient and robust solution for real-time asset health monitoring of external gear pump modules, which can be used within exhaust gas after-treatment systems, as shown in the use case of this article.

The article specifically summarizes the state of predictive maintenance and asset health monitoring of dosing systems and displacement machines, using exhaust gas after-treatment systems for large diesel vehicles as a case study. The paper presents a computationally efficient methodology based solely on hydraulic parameters that operates without time-sensitive data. The model enables the differentiation between wear in the machine driving the dosing system and wear within the dosing system itself. This distinction relies on simple physical equations and is inherently independent of the specific fluid system and the design of the displacement machine. The lightweight methodology is validated on external geared pumps, exploring various operating conditions to leverage hydraulic parameters for monitoring the pumping unit and dosing asset. The aim is to enhance asset health monitoring in dosing systems using a sparse methodology focused solely on hydraulic parameters, thereby improving overall efficiency and effectiveness.

1.1 Predictive Maintenance

Predictive maintenance is a preventive maintenance strategy. It aims to monitor the condition of assets and their components in real time, predict potential failures, and provide a prognosis for the remaining useful life (RUL) of the

asset. Through the use of sensors, data analytics, and machine learning, maintenance measures can be planned more efficiently (Lee et al. 2006). Therefore, predictive maintenance is an advancement of condition-based maintenance, building on the possibilities offered by digitalization (Holmberg and Adgar 2010). The understanding of asset degradation and its health monitoring is crucial for a model-based predictive maintenance. This enables both a health assessment and anomaly detection (Crespo Márquez 2022). The PF (Potential Failure to Functional Failure) curve is a foundational concept in predictive maintenance and asset health monitoring, providing a visual and analytical framework for understanding how equipment degrades over time (see Figure 1). By identifying the point at which a potential failure becomes detectable (Point P) and the point at which functional failure occurs (Point F) (Matyas 2022), organizations gain a critical window – the PF-interval – in which to act proactively. This concept enables actors to schedule interventions based on real asset conditions rather than relying on fixed intervals or reacting to unexpected breakdowns. The implications of the PF-curve are far-reaching: it supports the transition from reactive to preventive and predictive maintenance, reduces unplanned downtime, and optimizes resource allocation. Condition monitoring techniques such as vibration analysis, oil analysis, and thermal imaging, as well as operating parameters, such as the energy consumption rate, are integral to detecting early warning signs at Point P. The detected point P differs depending on the sensor signal used. The more critical an asset is, the longer the P-F interval should be defined. For example, a safety-critical asset should be monitored by vibration sensors instead of thermal imaging (cp. Figure 1).

The integration of additional sensors and machine learning further enhances the predictive power of the PF-curve by enabling continuous, real-time monitoring and more accurate failure prognostics. Successful implementation requires addressing challenges such as operational variability, data complexity, and bears the need for specialized expertise.

Figure 1: Example of a PF curve.

In practice, applying the PF-curve often encounters significant hurdles rooted in sensor and signal limitations, as many degradation processes begin at levels below an instrument’s resolution, leaving a blind spot before Point P. Operational variability, such as fluctuating loads, temperatures, or speeds, can mask accurate degradation signals and will either trigger false alarms or obscure genuine fault progression (Mallioris et al. 2024). The vast volumes of high-frequency data generated by continuous monitoring require a robust data handling and analytics infrastructure, which can strain both IT resources and organizational expertise. Establishing reliable failure thresholds is often challenging in real-world scenarios: overly conservative settings inflate maintenance costs through unnecessary interventions, while lax criteria risk unexpected breakdowns. Integrating PF-based prognostics into existing maintenance workflows requires cross-disciplinary coordination, as engineers must balance model outputs with practical considerations such as spare-part availability, workforce skills, and production schedules within the predictive maintenance approach (Teixeira et al. 2020). A continuous refinement of detection algorithms, combined with targeted training and governance frameworks, is therefore essential to translate PF-curve insights into real-world reliability gains.

1.2 Model-based Predictive Maintenance

Model-based predictive maintenance utilizes a clear understanding of the degradation model and the applicable PF-curve, along with its underlying physical failure model (Tinga and Loendersloot 2019) to enable Prognostics and Health Management (PHM) (IEEE Standard Framework for Prognostics and Health Management of Electronic Systems 2017). Realizing a model-based predictive maintenance with small data sets and low data handling procedures is meant to be lean predictive maintenance. It integrates the lean approach (Womack and Jones 1997). A wide range of model-based

approaches for condition monitoring is stated (Peng et al. 2010). Examining pumps and dosing systems reveals multiple options for condition monitoring (Beebe 2004). Previous studies have demonstrated the potential of utilizing data from flowmeters to monitor flow plant (Amadi-Echendu et al. 1993). The work presented here is based on these findings.

1.3 Pump Health Indicators

Various types of pumps exist, with centrifugal and positive displacement pumps being the two most commonly used. They differ in size, design, and the mechanism by which the pump delivers the fluid media. Two main design types categorize positive displacement machines: translational and rotational pumps. Fluid transport occurs through the displacement of elements, such as pistons, gears, or fluid chambers, which periodically move volumes to drive fluid flow. Centrifugal pumps, however, operate by converting rotational kinetic energy into hydrodynamic energy, using an impeller to accelerate the fluid outward and generate flow through centrifugal force (Volk 2013). The literature presents examples of intelligent applications for monitoring various pump modules that utilize classical machine learning algorithms and complex neural networks. These algorithms request time-dependent sensor data from the hydraulic machines and learn operating patterns from these complex datasets (Han et al. 2019).

However, it should be emphasized that these prognostic approaches are inherently time-dependent and strongly influenced by varying operating conditions. In particular, the useful life of pump components is not constant but varies significantly with load and operating regime, as increased stress accelerates wear. Consequently, accurate time-dependent prognostics require highly sophisticated algorithms and often rely on advanced neural network architectures to capture these complex, non-linear relationships. These models analyze time-dependent sensor data to identify anomalies in the signals, which in turn indicate potential faults in the pump units (Tao et al. 2024; Mohammed 2023). Furthermore, data-driven modeling methods can be used to express the behavior of the pump units and to develop a model of the existing machine based on this information. These model variants provide information about the operating behavior in real industrial scenarios and aim to predict the performance of the pump system (Han et al. 2019; Huang et al. 2020). The literature focuses on the wear effects of internal pump components, considering the entire application's lifetime, as the behavior of pump systems can change significantly over their lifespan. Complex machine learning algorithms classify pump behavior as either healthy or unhealthy. These complex mathematical algorithms require large datasets and are still impractical, considering the changing fluid systems, varying pump designs and especially the time dependent data structures (Xu et al. 2024; Lee et al. 2021). The application of simple physical laws, however, allows the usage of universally applicable methodologies (Guo et al. 2021). They are less frequently implemented as key building blocks within the monitoring of complex hydraulic systems.

Nevertheless, some sources still aim to predict hydraulic resistances using regression analyses or machine learning methods (Kumar et al. 2021; Bilgil and Altun 2008). However, these examples are limited to predicting simple hydraulic components and have not yet been utilized or validated in the context of hydraulic asset maintenance tools. Despite the growing use of advanced data-driven methods, a clear research gap persists in developing simple, lightweight, and transferable algorithms for pump monitoring. Current solutions rely primarily on computationally intensive models, limiting their deployment on low-resource systems. Additionally, predicting wear and degradation processes is rarely achieved with low-complexity approaches. The literature does not sufficiently emphasize the relationship between the pump and the system it drives. This distinction, however, is crucial for reliable monitoring and fault attribution, as system-level influences can significantly affect the measured signals, enabling more accurate and valuable insights for practical applications.

2 Proposed Method

2.1 Dosing Systems and Use Case

Pumping units and displacement machines are typically installed as a sub-process of a larger asset to perform a specific flow-related function. With that, the dosing system serves as an interface between the displacement machine and the overall system. Dosing systems are applied in various industries, including chemical manufacturing, pharmaceutical production, and waste treatment processes. Despite the ongoing digitalization and automation of industrial production processes, many industries continue to rely on traditional machinery to drive production, heavy-duty transport vehicles, and critical logistics operations. Diesel engines remain a vital component in such central drive systems for both mobile and stationary applications. Many industries widely use these machines because they offer strong performance and high torque output (Khan and Goga 2023). While environmental regulations are becoming more stringent, diesel engines remain a vital component in heavy-duty transportation and industrial operations, solidifying their global presence. To adhere to stricter emission regulations - especially those imposed by the European Commission - modern diesel vehicles heavily depend on advanced after-treatment systems at their exhaust designed to reduce harmful emissions (Regulation (EU) 2024/1610 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 May 2024 amending Regulation

(EU) 2019/1242 as regards strengthening the CO₂ emission performance standards for new heavy-duty vehicles and integrating reporting obligations, amending Regulation (EU) 2018/858 and repealing Regulation (EU) 2018/956). While after-treatment systems are essential for sustainable diesel operation, they add complex subsystems that require regular maintenance schedules (Rexeis and Hausberger 2009; Hoofman et al. 2018). These hydraulic subsystems require cautious scheduling routines with frequent inspections, resulting in increased operational costs for the users (Soleimani et al. 2018).

An exhaust gas treatment system of diesel engines is used as a scenario to illustrate the application of dynamically regulating dosing systems. As illustrated in Figure 2, the dosing system serves as a crucial component of the asset. In this industrial setting, displacement pumps inject a urea solution into the exhaust treatment process. The diesel engine emission gets mixed with the fluid solution provided by the dosing unit, thermally treated, and channeled into the selective catalytic reduction converter before finally exiting into the atmosphere. The displacement pump regulates the fluid solution dynamically in response to the load of the diesel engine. The control process, therefore, requires monitoring by intelligent sensors, as the volumetric flow rate, differential pressure, and temperature must be maintained during this process (Lakshmanan et al. 2023).

Figure 2: Exhaust gas treatment asset including dosing system.

The different components of the system can become worn or clogged over the asset's lifespan. Considering the scenario of an exhaust gas treatment system, this condition relates to the clogging of filtering systems, wear of the SCR catalytic converter, and degradation of the displacement pump. With varying operational conditions, including changing loads, catalytic converters often become clogged or degraded. This issue must be detected early to prolong the asset's lifespan and maintain the functionality of the gas treatment system (Soleimani et al. 2018). The urea solution can also harden via crystallization, which leads to clogging of the dosing system or greater abrasion of the components (Hlatká et al. 2021).

The system consists of the dynamic dosing unit, which includes the pump and sensors, and the primary static asset, representing the gas after-treatment process of the vehicle. The design of the pumping unit classifies the intended application into different sections. The most common systems utilize gear pumps configured as either internal or external pump designs. Due to their robust and slim design, this type of fluid machinery represents one of the most frequently used technologies, with a global market share of approximately 11%. The operational principle of these pump units is simple to understand. As shown in Figure 3, the operating process, including the energy chain of the pump's displacement machinery, can be simplified as follows:

Figure 3: Energy chain and operating process of the displacement machinery in a pump. P_e – electrical power, U – electrical voltage, I – electrical current, P_m – mechanical power, M – moment, n – rotational frequency, P_h – hydraulic power, Q – volumetric flow, p – pressure.

An electrical motor receives power and converts it into rotational motion. Through the gears, the fluid mass is displaced within the center of the pumping unit, i.e. the electrical power delivered is transformed into hydraulic power with an effective volume flow Q and an effective differential pressure p . The overall efficiency η_{total} of these machines can be expressed, considering DIN ISO 4391 and DIN ISO 4409, as the ratio between the effective hydraulic power P_h and the electrical power input P_e .

$$\eta_{total} = \frac{P_h}{P_e} \quad (1)$$

The efficiency of displacement machines, such as external gear pumps, depends on several key factors within the energy chain. However, the hydraulic power alone combines the target variables of the dosing system, including the differential pressure p and the volume flow Q . Therefore, an algorithm can solely utilize the hydraulic domain to monitor the functionality of the components. Figure 4 visualizes the interaction between the dynamic pumping unit and the primarily static asset as a representation of hydraulic resistances within the hydraulic domain:

Figure 4: Hydraulic domain of the displacement machine and the static asset. R_{pump} – hydraulic resistance of the pump unit, R_{eff} – effective hydraulic resistance of the static asset.

The pump displaces a fluid mass regardless of the connected asset as the gears intermesh according to the motor's rotation. The pumping unit can, therefore, be described as an ideal volumetric flow generator, which provides a theoretical volume flow Q_{theo} depending on its rotational frequency n (Mucchi et al. 2010a; Vacca and Guidetti 2011). However, the pump still attempts to overcome the hydraulic resistance R_{eff} within the static asset, resulting in an effective differential pressure Δp_{eff} . Depending on the operational conditions, a certain proportion of the displaced fluid mass flows back through the pumping unit, as the positive displacement machinery cannot seal the differential pressure ideally. The internal hydraulic losses Q_{loss} of the pump, therefore, relate to the effective volume flow Q_{eff} within the asset itself. Thus, the intersection between the pump curve field and the asset's hydraulic resistance curve

represents the effective operating point, which includes the volumetric flow Q_{eff} and the differential pressure Δp_{eff} . The asset must be seen as static within this scenario, as it does not actively contribute to forming the operational point.

The components of the internal flow field can characterize a hydraulic resistance R . Considering a low mean velocity over the cross-section of the flow, no vortices build up within the pipe. The leakage flow primarily exhibits laminar and steady streamlines within the narrow gaps between the gear tips, gear faces and the housing, and also within the journal bearings. The hydraulic resistance exhibits a linear correlation $\zeta_{laminar}$ between pressure and flow within these laminar structures. The linear relationship between pressure and flow rate must be extended by a quadratic term with the parameter ζ_{vortex} , assuming a higher velocity within the pipe system, as vortices can form within the flow. Vortices arise, for example, in the pump's inflow and outflow regions, which often involve complex piping networks with contractions, and due to the gear intermeshing process at the pump outlet. A second-order polynomial equation represents the relationship between pressure and flow rate within a complex pipe network, see the curve for the static asset in Figure 5. An external static pressure resembles the bias of p_0 within Equation 2 (Engler 2006):

$$\Delta p = \zeta_{vortex} \cdot Q^2 + \zeta_{laminar} \cdot Q + p_0 \quad (2)$$

The static asset, which includes the gas after-treatment process, resembles such a complex pipe network, which can be expressed as a second-order function, regardless of the fluid system used or its specific physical properties. The hydraulic resistance R_{eff} , however, can increase or decrease over varying temperatures as the physical properties of the fluid system change (Halonen et al. 2017). If the average surface cross-section of a pipe alternates due to changing valve positions, this hydraulic resistance can vary (Engler 2006).

Figure 5: Schematic overview of the interaction between the pumping unit and the connected static asset.

The internal sealing resistance R_{pump} of the pumping unit also follows a second-order polynomial relationship, considering only one rotational frequency n . Since this rotational frequency determines the output of the pump unit, an entire curve field emerges in the case of a positive displacement pump. The pump's curve field represents the operating range in the hydraulic domain. The intersection points between the curve field of the pump and the hydraulic resistance of the connected static asset part represent the operating points of the system (see Figure 5). Depending on the application, the pump module must respond dynamically, as both the target volume flow within the asset and the necessary differential pressure that the pump unit tries to overcome can change based on environmental conditions (Rundo 2017; Mucchi et al. 2010a; Mucchi et al. 2010b). This outlined relationship between the pumping unit and the static asset is fundamental for establishing the quadrant model for lean predictive maintenance of dosing systems and was previously introduced and systematically illustrated in our earlier work (Peric et al. 2026).

2.2 Modeling Approach

2.2.1 Representing Pump and Asset Life Span as Altering Hydraulic Resistances

Suppose the average surface cross-section of a pipe does not alternate due to external influences within a specific period of time. In that case, the model-based predictive maintenance management tool can distinguish between monitoring the static asset part and the pumping unit by simply using only the context of the hydraulic domain. The operating conditions refer to the relationship between the differential pressure and the effective volumetric flow rate (Figure 6).

The operating point encompasses the asset's behavior within the hydraulic resistance, as well as the characteristics of the pumping unit within the intersection of the operating point. The model-based approach tracks and predicts the dynamic operating point depending on the pump's characteristics. The hydraulic resistance changes if the pumping curve alternates due to wear of the pump components, when internal clogging within the asset emerges, or even if a fatal error within the system arises. These changes cause variations in the hydraulic resistances. For this reason, we include a case distinction within the model. The model shall detect both asset components, the dynamic pump unit and the static pipe network of the asset. Figure 6 contains a detailed visualization of the model elements, which interpret the pump's and the asset's behavior as hydraulic resistances. Changes within these resistances allow a prediction of potential failure occurrence (Khoshzaban-Zavarehi 2009).

Figure 6: Hydraulic resistances as building blocks for the PHM tool, op – operating point, a) changing hydraulic resistances within the asset, b) altering hydraulic resistances of the pump curve behavior over its entire life span.

The first step is to determine to what extent the hydraulic resistance of a system can alter and what changes occur in the operating procedure. Considering the healthy state of the asset, one single hydraulic resistance emerges within the operating cycle. Consequently, all operating points of an application are formed via the second-degree polynomial of the hydraulic resistance. The primary objective of the fluid machinery is to transport a specified volumetric fluid flow, taking into account the present hydraulic resistance. The control of the fluid machinery, therefore, dynamically contracts the shift of the operating point along the hydraulic resistance, which represents the relationship between the pressure and the effective volume flow values. As a result, the control architecture of a displacement machine intrinsically incorporates the hydraulic relationships among pressure, volume flow, and rotational frequency of the pumping unit. It is worth noting that the control architecture itself can be implemented through this correlation between the rotational frequency, the volume flow, and the differential pressure.

If a blockage occurs within the pipe network, the internal resistance increases. A leakage within the system represents a short circuit of pipe components, which ultimately leads to a reduction in the hydraulic resistance. The smaller the effective volume flow Q_{eff} , the more pronounced these changes become as the curves converge at the origin (Figure 6a).

The behavior of a pump can change over its lifetime. Figure 6 shows a single pump curve, which only represents a single rotational frequency. The pump design, including the internal gaps and the physical properties of the pumped fluid, determines the overall performance, the resulting characteristic pump curve, and the entire pumping curve field. If a certain amount of abrasion occurs within the pump, the sealing ability diminishes. The characteristic curve flattens out over the pump's lifespan (Guo et al. 2020). The displacement within the meshing zone of the gears can also be harmed if the teeth of the pump experience heavy wear. A fatal breakage of the pump components, such as a breakage of a single tooth, can also be described by a changed pump curve (Konieczny and Stojek 2021). Consequently, it must be considered that the pump characteristic curve will flatten out over its life span of the pump and that it, therefore, generates a lower differential pressure Δp_{eff} (Figure 6b) (Konieczny et al. 2023). A steeper pump characteristic curve should not be assumed in this scenario, as the behavior of the pumping unit typically does not improve its efficiency with usage.

2.2.2 Implementation Procedure and Interpretation of Failures

The model-based approach detects changes within the effective volume flow rate Q_{eff} and the differential pressure Δp_{eff} . The procedure determines the target operating point using a second-degree polynomial (Equation 2) that illustrates the relationship between volume flow and differential pressure, representing the asset's hydraulic resistance. In this context, the laminar resistance and turbulent resistances are represented as the parameters a_x within the procedure:

$$\Delta p_{\text{eff}}(Q_{\text{eff}}) = a_1 \cdot Q_{\text{eff}}^2 + a_2 \cdot Q_{\text{eff}} + a_3 \quad (3)$$

As the operating point moves along this parabola at varying pump rotational frequencies n , each frequency n corresponds to a specific differential pressure Δp_{eff} and volumetric flow rate Q_{eff} . The change of the pump's quadratic characteristic curve is thus reflected by the system curve (Equation 3), which in turn represents the quadratic relationship between volumetric flow Q_{eff} and differential pressure Δp_{eff} . Therefore, a higher-degree polynomial is used to represent the relationship between rotational speed n and volumetric flow Q_{model} .

$$Q_{\text{model}}(n) = a_4 \cdot n^3 + a_5 \cdot n^2 + a_6 \cdot n + a_7 \quad (4)$$

The quadratic terms within the asset's hydraulic resistance, however, incorporate the calculation of the corresponding differential pressure Δp_{model} .

$$\Delta p_{\text{model}}(Q_{\text{model}}) = a_1 \cdot Q_{\text{model}}^2 + a_2 \cdot Q_{\text{model}} + a_3 \quad (5)$$

Using these two equations, each rotational speed can be assigned a specific volumetric flow rate and corresponding differential pressure in a teaching process. These model predictions must be automatically determined and registered during the Teach-In procedure. Consequently, the model only requires the regression of two simple equations. These equations describe the correlation among rotational speed, volumetric flow, and differential pressure in a healthy system. The following figure illustrates how the relationship among these three parameters can be used to assess wear-related effects.

Figure 7: Implementation procedure of the quadrant model.

The Teach-In process involves the regression of Equations (4) and (5), in which the seven parameters a_1 to a_7 must be determined. The Teach-In process characterizes the behavior of the healthy dosing system and the non-worn, fully operational pump. The model predictions Δp_{model} and Q_{model} incorporate the healthy operating states of the components and can subsequently be used as health indicators by comparing them with the volumetric flows Q_{eff} and differential pressures Δp_{eff} during operation, in which wear occurs within the components. For this purpose, a simple vector can be calculated:

$$\vec{v} = \begin{pmatrix} Q_{eff} - Q_{model} \\ \Delta p_{eff} - \Delta p_{model} \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The magnitude and angle of the resulting vector \vec{v} between the model prediction and the monitored operating point serve as a key metric. The vector's starting point is dynamic and changes with the rotational frequency, since the operating point also varies along the initial system characteristic line (Equation 3). The larger the vector's span, the more significant the changes in the system. Furthermore, the vector's direction indicates which specific component is

experiencing wear and allows differentiation, as it points in different directions depending on whether only the pump is degrading, a leakage occurs in the dosing system, or both components are aging simultaneously.

Consequently, the quadrant model of the asset management tool must always be applied to the target operating point, which incorporates the pump's rotational frequency n and the hydraulic resistance of the asset. The center of the quadrant model, therefore, varies dynamically depending on the pump's operational conditions, which primarily involve mapping the rotational frequency within the hydraulic domain. The following three scenarios symbolize the functionality of the quadrant model:

Figure 8: Interpretation of the resulting vector \vec{V} using the quadrant model of the asset management tool, a) Functionality of the quadrant model and interpretation of the vector, b) Application of the quadrant model within the application.

Throughout the asset's lifespan, its components experience wear or may become jammed. In the context of an exhaust gas treatment system, this issue refers to the clogging or deterioration of the filtering system. Considering the heavy demands and varying environmental conditions, these system components become clogged, which frequently results in system failure. This situation results in an increased hydraulic resistance within the system. A higher differential pressure Δp_{eff} and a lower volume flow rate Q_{eff} emerge, considering the same rotational frequency n (quadrant II), compared to the predicted volume flow Q_{model} and the differential pressure Δp_{model} of the original operating points. If the pump experiences faults or wear but the asset remains in healthy condition, the operating point shifts to a different quadrant (quadrant III). Increased internal losses due to pump degradation or malfunction result in reduced efficiency. Consequently, the pump is unable to produce the required volume flow and differential pressure, i.e., both the differential pressure Δp_{eff} and the volume flow Q_{eff} drop, resulting in a shift of the operating point. Changes occur through leakage in the system, component failure due to external factors, or if the fluid mass escapes from the pipe network to an unintended external area. This leakage acts like a short circuit, allowing fluid to flow out through the breach instead of through the desired pipe network. As a result, the overall hydraulic resistance decreases. The volume flow increases while the differential pressure drops, reaching the third operating scenario (quadrant IV).

Comparing the target and actual operating points provides valuable insights into the interaction between the static asset and the pump module. This method helps to identify and assess the level of asset health, where the resulting vector between the target and the actual operating point serves as the metric. By calculating its magnitude and considering its direction, it is possible to identify the type and extent of the fault without the need for complex algorithms. In direct comparison to the PF-curve, the quadrant model does not consider the time domain. Degradation within the system components is detected solely by observing hydraulic parameters. A substantial change in the resulting vector indicates strong environmental influences or a fatal error. Events of significantly changing conditions, such as irregular temperature fluctuations or a pipe break, trigger an increased magnitude of the resulting vector. Smaller vector magnitudes, on the other hand, indicate slight wear of the components. However, after maintenance has been carried

out, such as replacing the filter, the entire implementation procedure as depicted in Figure 7 must be repeated from start to finish, as the hydraulic resistance of the asset may change and a new operating point may be set. However, the procedure can be effectively implemented on microcontrollers, as the curve regressions require minimal computational effort and minimal data.

3 Experimental Setup

To demonstrate the applicability of the outlined quadrant model for asset health monitoring as a basis for lean predictive maintenance, several experiments were conducted within a dosing system test rig. The quadrant model utilizes the data and processes it to allow the interpretation of the system changes.

3.1 Test Rig

In this test rig, an external gear pump operates within a closed hydraulic circuit, as illustrated in Figure 9. Sensors are positioned around the pump to monitor the exact volume flow, temperature, and differential pressure across the inlet and outlet of the pump. The setup also includes drain valves and a vent to counteract any undesirable pressure build-up that might interfere with measurements. Additionally, a 5-liter tank provides the fluid for the closed system. The mounting frame has been designed to minimize vibrations from the experimental pumps.

Figure 9: Schematic overview of the test rig.

This setup enables the investigation of three different scenarios:

1. The pump behavior is measured using water to provide reference data under ideal laboratory conditions. This section covers the entire operating range of the pumps, including various temperatures.
2. A urea solution is added to the tank to examine the fluid dosing system of a gas after-treatment process. Changing valve positions resolve different hydraulic resistances of the static asset part. Additionally, a filter system with a bypass is added to replicate real-life operational conditions within this scenario.
3. Finally, a water solution with test dust, as specified in ISO 12103-1, is incorporated to create controllable degradation of the pump units. This procedure allows the measurement of the entire pump's life cycle.

Table 1 contains the specifications of the test rig to ensure the replicability of the experiment.

Component	Model / Manufacturer
Volume flow meter	Sonotec – SONOFLOW IL.52
Pressure sensors	STS Sensors – ATM/T and IFM Electronic – PT5494
Thermometer	PT100 – IEC 751 (EN 60751)
Pumping units	SDU 2876 (A) and 4080 (B) (Scherzinger Pumpen)
Filtering system	Wrapped filter cartridges – Putsch GmbH & Co. KG
Bypass	Two-way ball valves – Rötelmann GmbH
Control valves	M-Flow 25 – Vögtlin Instruments GmbH

Table 1: Used measurement and system components.

3.2 Features of Data Sets

The dataset comprises measurements from a total of eight pumps, divided equally into two pump batches: batch A and batch B, each containing four pumps. Batch A includes a total of 5,798 data points, while batch B consists of 7,196 data points. Measurements include five distinct temperatures: 10 °C, 20 °C, 30 °C, 40 °C, and 50 °C. These points represent a broad thermal spectrum, allowing for an accurate validation of condition monitoring across the entire temperature range of the used pumping units. The rotational frequency for the pumps in batch A spans from 400 to 4,000 rpm. The pumps in batch B have a narrower rotational speed range, from 200 to 2,200 rpm, reflecting the two different pump designs. Both batches cover the entire operating range of the respective pumps in terms of differential pressure and volumetric flow rate. The maximum differential pressure is limited to 8 bar across all measurements. The volumetric flow rate does not exceed 1,000 ml/min for pumps in batch A, and 7,000 ml/min for pumps in batch B.

4 Results

The discussion of the results is divided into three sections. It includes the proof that the pure use of hydraulic domains enables a more accurate interpretation of the system behavior in the context of an asset management tool. The chapter demonstrates that the hydraulic resistance accurately incorporates the asset's and pump's behavior as second order polynomials under real conditions. Finally, the chapter illustrates the validation of the quadrant model, including the extent to which the quadrant model can detect pump degradation due to wear and failures within the static asset.

4.1 Proof of Concept: Using Hydraulic Domain Variables as Key Factors for PHM

The validation of the PHM tool relies on the usage of control variables from the hydraulic domain. The remaining control variables, such as increased load capacities of the pump motor or system vibrations due to wear degradation, are purposely disregarded. To prove this thesis, the validation procedure primarily incorporates a comparison between electrical and hydraulic control variables. The validation consists of a regression analysis of the pump curves, as illustrated in Figure 10. For contrast, a linear multivariable regression analysis is implemented. This procedure resembles fitting a simple plane in three dimensions. Here, the volume flow, differential pressure, current, and voltage define the basis for predicting the corresponding rotational frequency of the pump. Figure 10 includes the validation of pump module no. 1 under laboratory conditions using water at a temperature of 20 °C:

Figure 10: Comparison between electrical and hydraulic domains – the relationship between rotational frequency and system variables (a – electrical domain, including voltage and current of the pumping unit, b – hydraulic domain, including pressure and volume flow of the pumping unit).

The regression analysis demonstrates the relation between the pump's rotational frequency and the system's control variables. The left-hand side shows the interconnection between the input variables of the motor that drives the pump and its rotational speed. The right-hand side displays the relationship between the hydraulic power of the pump and its rotational frequency. The correlation between the electrical power fed in and the rotational frequency of the gears shows deviations. Considering the energy conversion chain of the fluid machine, these variations represent the varying efficiency losses throughout the energy conversion process. These include the motor's energy conversion and the friction losses of the gear components, which could result from forces and vibration patterns. The relation between the rotational frequency and the effective hydraulic power can be captured much more accurately (Figure 10, b). The displacement of the fluid mass by the gear mesh, including internal volume flow losses within the pump, represents the correlation between pressure, volume flow rate, and the rotational frequency of the gears.

Table 2: First-order regression analysis of hydraulic and electric domains

	Pump no. 1			Pump no. 2		
	MAE	MAPE	R^2	MAE	MAPE	R^2
hydraulic domain	49.99 rpm	3.81 %	0.995	27.21 rpm	4.35 %	0.9969
electric domain	486.22 rpm	33.11 %	0.62334	122.63 rpm	18.30 %	0.8984

* These results contain the average over all temperatures from 10 °C to 50 °C, including MAE (Mean Absolute Error), MAPE (Mean Absolute Percentage Error), and R^2 (coefficient of determination).

The energy conversion between the electrical and mechanical domains shows greater variation than the conversion between the mechanical and hydraulic control variables. The validation, therefore, indicates that it is reasonable to use purely hydraulic parameters and dispense with electrical input variables to implement accurate and precise monitoring of system behavior. A simple multidimensional linear regression, however, cannot fully grasp the relationship between the target rotational frequency and the system variables. This simple linear modeling approach, therefore, is not suitable for fully representing the behavior of the underlying pumping units. However, the relationship can nevertheless be predicted with a high degree of accuracy, considering the operational rotational frequencies within the hydraulic domain, with an error rate of approximately 4 %.

4.2 Validation: Using Hydraulic Resistances as the Key Building Blocks for Lean Predictive Maintenance

It is further necessary to improve the accuracy and to include the turbulence formation of fluid within the hydraulic domain, which corresponds to a quadratic term. This quadratic equation represents the full hydraulic resistance of a complex flow field, which is used within the framework of the quadrant model to grasp the behavior of the pump and the asset.

Table 3 presents the validation of the core building block for the quadrant model, considering second-degree polynomials as hydraulic resistances for the pumps and the assets' hydraulic resistance. Here, both the asset's behavior and the pump characteristics curves are mapped individually as second-order polynomials. A pump characteristic curve represents measurements taken at a specific rotational frequency. However, different valve positions imitate a change in the asset's behavior as depicted in Figure 5. Capturing an asset curve must, vice versa, include only one valve constellation; thus, it must implement different rotational frequencies to capture changing pressure and volumetric flow values over the hydraulic resistance. The following figure shows the regression of the pump characteristic curves and the static assets. The same dataset is used here, namely Pump 1 at a temperature of 20 °C:

Figure 11: Comparison between the fit of a pump's characteristic curve and a static asset curve (Pump 1-A at $T = 20$ °C): (a) polynomial fit of pump curves; (b) polynomial fit of static asset curves.

The MAPE values remain low for both the pump curves and the static asset curves, as Table 3 shows. For the pump curves, the maximum MAPE is 1.89 % (Pump 1 – A), corresponding to an absolute pressure error of 0.0177 bar at nominal conditions. For the static asset curves, the maximum MAPE also reaches 1.89 % (Pump 6 – B), with an absolute pressure error of 0.0357 bar. Overall, the R^2 values are very close to 1, indicating excellent agreement between the fitted curves and the measured data. The pump characteristic curves can be represented across all temperatures with a mean MAPE of 1.33 %, while the static asset curves exhibit a mean MAPE of 1.57 %.

Table 3: Second-order regression analysis for pump and static asset behavior curves representing hydraulic resistances

Pump number	Pump curve			Static asset curve		
	MAE [bar]	MAPE [%]	R^2	MAE [bar]	MAPE [%]	R^2
1 – A	0.0177	1.89	0.9995	0.0429	1.67	0.9899
2 – A	0.0204	1.57	0.9991	0.0271	1.23	0.9992
3 – A	0.0154	1.31	0.9997	0.0403	1.56	0.9987
4 – A	0.0153	1.32	0.9997	0.0372	1.44	0.9984
5 – B	0.0115	1.05	0.9999	0.0361	1.82	0.9981
6 – B	0.0129	1.14	0.9998	0.0357	1.89	0.9978
7 – B	0.0092	0.77	0.9999	0.0277	1.48	0.9986
8 – B	0.0177	1.61	0.9998	0.0298	1.57	0.9986

* These results contain the average over all temperatures from 10 °C to 50 °C, including MAE (Mean Absolute Error), MAPE (Mean Absolute Percentage Error), and R^2 (coefficient of determination).

4.3 Validation: Quadrant Model for Asset Health Monitoring

The quadrant model serves as a comprehensive monitoring tool. The approach tracks the operating point dynamically, adjusting it according to the current rotational frequency. Here, the volume flow, as well as the pressure, must be calculated based on the rotational frequency to function as a target operating point for the quadrant model. Table 4 presents the validation of the chained regression analysis, which considers the prediction of the target operating point for the quadrant model.

Table 4: Validation of the quadrant model: regression analysis of the target operating points

Pump number	Volume flow prediction: $Q_m(n_{rot})$			Differential pressure prediction: $p_m(Q_m)$		
	MAE [ml/min]	MAPE [%]	$\sigma(Q_m)$ [ml/min]	MAE [bar]	MAPE [%]	$\sigma(p_m)$ [bar]
1 – A	0.83	0.59	1.08	0.06	2.49	0.07
2 – A	0.52	0.35	0.67	0.02	0.96	0.03
3 – A	0.60	0.40	0.77	0.03	1.40	0.04
4 – A	0.60	0.39	0.76	0.03	1.38	0.04
5 – B	2.44	0.35	3.16	0.03	1.67	0.04
6 – B	2.32	0.13	3.01	0.03	1.85	0.04
7 – B	2.66	0.15	3.49	0.03	1.43	0.03
8 – B	3.25	0.14	4.10	0.04	1.55	0.03

* These results contain the average over all temperatures from 10 °C to 50 °C, including MAE (Mean Absolute Error), MAPE (Mean Absolute Percentage Error), and σ (standard deviation).

The prediction of the pressure values has a slightly higher error rate, considering the percentage error. This circumstance can be traced back to the chaining of the regression errors. The prediction of the volume flow rate using a third-order polynomial is used to calculate the target differential pressure based on the detected hydraulic resistance of the asset. The error rate of the volume flow prediction is therefore linked to the prediction of the pressure values.

The quadrant model is illustrated below in Figure 11, which visualizes changes in the asset behavior as well as the effects of pump wear degradation within the temperature range of 20 °C. The model can detect a potential wearing process across all pumps with a mean standard deviation of $\sigma(Q_m) = 2.31$ ml/min for the volume flow monitoring and $\sigma(p_m) = 0.04$ bar for the differential pressure. This relatively high accuracy demonstrates the sensitivity of the lightweight modeling approach across the entire operating range of the fluid machinery.

Figure 12: Quadrant model visualization of Pump No. 2-A: a) nominal values, b) relative changes.

Figure 11 illustrates the quadrant model approach. It presents 12 distinct pump operating conditions, each represented by a normalized value in the range 0 to 1 for changing rotational frequencies. The quadrant model enables, in particular, the differentiation between pump degradation states and system degradation. Depending on the system's operating state and the characteristics of its resistance curve, pump leakage has varying levels of impact.

The calculated vector values are located in the third quadrant only if the pump shows degradation and the asset remains intact. Pump degradation results in a 40% reduction in differential pressure and a 20% decrease in volumetric flow rate within the measurements. If an aged or clogged filter is also present in the dosing system, the effective volumetric flow rate decreases by approximately 40%, and the differential pressure increases significantly by up to 300% due to increased system resistance. Within a clogged filter system, pump degradation primarily affects pressure generation in the second quadrant. In relative terms, the differential pressure is reduced from 300% to approximately 60% due to pump wear. Nevertheless, based on the vector's location within the second quadrant and the angle of the operating vector, it is clearly identifiable that both significant pump degradation and a high degree of filter clogging are present.

Furthermore, Figure 11 shows artificially induced leakage from opening a bypass. In this case, the operating vector shifts into the fourth quadrant. Due to the reduced system resistance caused by the bypass opening, the differential pressure drops significantly by nearly 60%. As a result, even a healthy pump cannot generate a substantial differential pressure increase under these conditions. In this operating state, pump degradation primarily results in a 20% reduction in volumetric flow rate. Overall, the quadrant model allows both nominal and relative assessment of pump conditions while accounting for system behavior.

5 Summary

5.1 Conclusion

This paper presents a method for monitoring and interpreting a dosing system that incorporates pumping machines and connected hydraulic asset parts. The methodology implements a condition monitoring process within the scenario of a gas after-treatment system, which only includes the differential pressure, the effective volume flow rate, and the pump's current rotational frequency. The model neglects the electrical control variables of the pump motor. It does not need additional condition monitoring sensors, such as sensitive vibration sensors. The behavior of the system's components, including the pump unit and the hydraulic asset, is substituted as simple quadratic hydraulic resistances. Individual speed-dependent pump characteristic curves can be expressed as second-degree polynomials between the volume flow rate and the differential pressure, with a percentage error rate of approximately 1.33%. This approach enables the representation of the asset's behavior in the case studies with an error rate of 1.58% based on the MAPE. The quadrant model detects a malfunctioning of the dosing system within the hydraulic domain. Signs of wear degradation on the pump units and changes in operating conditions due to a system's blockage or leakage consequently produce varying hydraulic resistances. A comparison between the intact operating point of the model predictions and the system changes that occur takes place via a mapping over the existing rotational frequency. The model predicts the target volume flow rates with an average percentage error of 0.312% and a target differential pressure of 1.59%, considering the MAPE. The quadrant model ultimately allows the interpretation of the system states within these error ranges.

5.2 Discussion

The quadrant model is a lean approach toward realizing predictive maintenance in the diverse field of dosing system implementations. This model enables the time-sensitive identification of evolving asset failures without relying on either intensive condition monitoring techniques or computationally intensive asset data models. The use of the vector's magnitude and angle as indicators for asset health allows for continuous and low-cost health monitoring. For the dosing asset system use case, a simple differentiation into four different health quadrants provides information on where possible asset health issues originate, either from the dynamic pump or the static asset part. However, further validation about the extent of health diminution and the magnitude of the vector between the target and real operating point, as well as the direction of this vector, shall be done. As always, this model, intended to be simple, currently only allows the definition of groups of health issues (quadrants II-IV). For more detailed information on the evolving problem within the static dosing asset part and the pump, further research and a more detailed description of the quadrant model are required.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Benjamin Peric: Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. Katja Gutsche: Writing – original draft. Michael Engler: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Formal analysis, Conceptualization, Methodology. Peter Woias: Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

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